

The Effect of Substituents on the Basic Strengths of 4-Methylthio- and 4-Methylsulphonylanilines

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The ionisation constants of chloro, iodo and nitro substituted 4-methylthioanilines and chloro substituted 4-methylsulphonylanilines have been determined in aqueous solution by the spectrophotometric method at 30°. The principle of additivity of group influences has been examined. The results show that there is good additivity, when substituents are present in both the *ortho* positions to the amino group. The departure from additivity is observed, when similar substituents (chloro or iodo) are placed on either side of the methylthio group. The deviations have been discussed.

The effect of multiple substitution on the reactivity of a functional group in the benzene ring is expressed by the equation

$$\log K/K_0 = \rho \Sigma\sigma^1.$$

Crocker and Jones² claim that the group influences are additive, except for groups placed adjacent to the methoxy group. However, Stone and Pearson³ have raised the question as to whether the influences of substituents on reactivity are additive. They have concluded from a study of the ionisation constants of trisubstituted benzoic acids that the additivity holds true only upto three vicinal ethyl groups. Recently, Dippy and Hughes⁴ examined the principle of additivity with respect to the strengths of 34 disubstituted benzoic acids and concluded that the cumulative effect of substituents in the benzene ring is not strictly additive, even in the absence of supplementary steric and mesomeric interactions. Robinson⁵ also observed that in the case of 2, 6-disubstituted phenols, the additivity principle fails. However, he found that there is a linear relationship between disubstituted phenols and anilines (the substituent being chloro) containing at least one substituent in the *ortho* position. The present work was undertaken with a view to study the effect of multiple substitution on the strength of 4-methylthioaniline. Our results fail to give unequivocal support for the additivity principle. The effect of substituents (chloro) on the strength of 4-methylsulphonylaniline has also been investigated.

EXPERIMENTAL

2-Chloro-, 3-chloro-, 2,6-dichloro-, and 2-nitro-4-methylthioanilines and 2-chloro-4-methylsulphonylaniline were prepared by the procedures described in the literature.

1. H. H. Jaffe, *Chem. Rev.*, 1953, **53**, 243.
2. H. P. Crocker and B. Jones, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1959, 1808.
3. R. M. Stone and D. E. Pearson, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1961, **26**, 257.
4. J. F. J. Dippy and S. R. C. Hughes, *Tetrahedron*, 1963, **19**, 1527.
5. R. A. Robinson, *J. Res. Natl. Bur. Stds.*, 1964, **68A**, 159.

The substituted 4-thiocyanoanilines prepared by the method of Shibataka Kichina⁶ are listed in Table I along with their physical constants and analytical data. The substituted 4-methylthioanilines prepared from the corresponding 4-thiocyanoanilines by the method of Sawicki and Carr¹⁰ are also recorded in Table I.

TABLE I

Aniline	M.P.	Solvent	Formula		Percentage of			
					C	H	N	S
3-Iodo-4-thiocyano	79-80°	aq. EtOH	C ₇ H ₅ IN ₂ S	Found	30.62	1.96	9.98	11.48
				Reqd.	30.45	1.83	10.15	11.61
2-Iodo-4-thiocyano	91-92°	aq. EtOH	C ₇ H ₅ IN ₂ S	Found	30.56	1.86	10.22	11.48
				Reqd.	30.45	1.83	10.15	11.61
3,5-Diiodo-4-thio- cyano	199-200° (decomp.)	acetone	C ₇ H ₄ I ₂ N ₂ S	Found	21.02	1.06	7.12	8.02
				Reqd.	20.91	1.00	6.97	7.98
3-Nitro-4-thio- cyano	150-51°	aq. EtOH	C ₇ H ₅ N ₃ O ₂ S	Found	43.16	2.66	21.52	16.36
				Reqd.	43.08	2.58	21.53	16.43
3-Iodo-4-methyl- thio	88-89°	aq. EtOH	C ₇ H ₈ INS	Found	31.91	3.12	5.24	11.96
				Reqd.	31.71	3.04	5.28	12.09
3,5-Diiodo-4- methylthio	71-72°	acetone	C ₇ H ₇ I ₂ NS	Found	21.63	1.68	3.62	8.25
				Reqd.	21.50	1.80	3.58	8.20
3-Nitro-4-methyl- thio	122-23°	aq. EtOH	C ₇ H ₈ N ₂ O ₂ S	Found	45.42	4.28	14.96	17.62
				Reqd.	45.64	4.38	15.21	17.40
2,6-Dinitro-4- methylthio	84-85°	aq. EtOH	C ₇ H ₇ N ₃ O ₄ S	Found	36.44	3.10	18.52	14.06
				Reqd.	36.68	3.08	18.33	13.98
2,5-Dichloro-4- methylthio	103-04°	CH ₃ OH	C ₇ H ₇ Cl ₂ NS	Found	40.15	3.52	6.88	15.24
				Reqd.	40.40	3.39	6.73	15.40

2,6-Dichloro-4-nitrothiophenol was prepared from 3,4,5-trichloronitrobenzene by the procedure adopted by Price and Stacy⁷ for the preparation of *p*-nitrothiophenol. The product was recrystallised from aqueous ethanol to give yellow needles melting at 84-85°. (Found: C, 32.25; H, 1.25; N, 6.32; S, 14.47%. C₆H₃Cl₂NO₂S requires C, 32.17; H, 1.35; N, 6.25; S, 14.30%.

3,5-Dichloro-4-methylthionitrobenzene.—2,6-Dichloro-4-nitrothiophenol (7.8 g) was dissolved in a solution of sodium hydroxide (1.5 g) in water (20ml). The solution was cooled in ice and freshly distilled dimethyl sulphate (4.4 g) was added in small portions with stirring. After the addition was over, the solution was heated on a water bath at 70° for 30 min., cooled and the yellow solid that separated was collected by filtration. On recrystallisation from aqueous ethanol, it gave pale yellow needles of 3,5-dichloro-4-methylthionitrobenzene (6.0 g) which melted at 64-65°. (Found: C, 35.17; H, 2.16; N, 5.76; S, 13.30%. C₇H₅Cl₂NO₂S requires C, 35.31; H, 2.12; N, 5.88; S, 13.46%). 3,5-Dichloro-4-methylthioaniline was obtained by reducing the above compound with iron and hydrochloric acid, following essentially the method described by Novello, Bell, Abrams, Ziegler and Sprague.⁸ Recrystallisation from aqueous ethanol gave pale yellow crystals melting at 122-123° (lit.⁹ m.p. 122°).

6. Shibataka Kichina, Japan, ('60) *Appl. Mar.*, 19, 1958.

7. C. C. Price and G. W. Stacy, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1946, **68**, 498.

8. F. C. Novello, S. C. Bell, E. L. A. Abrams, C. Ziegler, and J. M. Sprague, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1960, **25**, 965.

9. S. Oae and C. C. Price, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1958, **80**, 4938.

2-Iodo-4-methylthioaniline is a liquid and it decomposed on attempting distillation under reduced pressure in an inert atmosphere. Hence, it was purified by repeated extraction with ether and hydrochloric acid and regenerating the base after each extraction.

The spectrophotometric method adopted for determining the ionisation constants is similar to that devised by Robinson.¹¹ The spectra were recorded in duplicate, with a Beckman Model DU spectrophotometer. Citrate buffers were used for compounds having $pK_a > 3$ and hydrochloric acid solutions for compounds with $pK_a < 3$ and > -0.5 . For very weak bases with $pK_a < -0.5$, sulphuric acid solutions were used.

From the observed absorbances, the pK_a values were calculated using the expression

$$pK_a = pH - \log \frac{(D_1 - D)}{(D - D_2)} + \log f_{RNH_3^+}$$

where D_1 and D_2 are the absorbances of the ion and the free base and D , the absorbance of the base in the buffer or in acid solutions; $f_{RNH_3^+}$ is the activity coefficient of the conjugate acid of the base. In the case of sulphuric acid solutions, acidity functions were used instead of pH in the calculations.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The pK_a values of 4-methylthioanilines and 4-methylsulphonylanilines in aqueous solution at 30° and the decrement in the pK_a values due to ring substitution, are given in Table II.

TABLE II

Decrement in pK_a Values on Ring Substitution

Aniline	pK_a at 30°	$-\Delta pK_a$ (obsd)	$-\Delta pK_a$ (calcd. assuming additivity)
4-Methylthio	4.31*	—	—
3-Chloro-4-methylthio	3.38	0.93	—
3,5-Dichloro-4-methylthio	1.67	2.64	0.93 + 0.93 (1.86)
3-Iodo-4-methylthio	3.44	0.87	—
3,5-Diiodo-4-methylthio	1.15	3.16	0.87 + 0.87 (1.74)
2-Iodo-4-methylthio	2.45	1.86	—
2-Chloro-4-methylthio	2.56	1.75	—
2,5-Dichloro-4-methylthio	1.70	2.61	1.75 + 0.93 (2.68)
2,6-Dichloro-4-methylthio	0.35	3.96	1.75 + 1.75 (3.50)
3-Nitro-4-methylthio	2.47	1.84	—
2-Nitro-4-methylthio	-0.28	4.59	—
2,6-Dinitro-4-methylthio	-4.46	8.77	4.59 + 4.59 (9.18)
4-Methylsulphonyl	1.46*	—	—
2-Chloro-4-methylsulphonyl	-0.41	1.87	—
3-Chloro-4-methylsulphonyl	0.47	0.99	—

*N. Vanajakshi, Ph.D. Thesis, Madras University, 1967.

10. E. Sawicki and A. Carr, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1957, **22**, 503.

11. R. A. Robinson, "Structure of Electrolytic Solutions." W. J. Hamer, ed., John Wiley and Sons, Inc., New York, 1959, Chap. 16.

The introduction of chloro, iodo and nitro groups in the *meta* position to the amino group (*i.e.*, in the *ortho* position to the methylthio group) in 4-methylthioaniline reduces the basic strength mainly due to the electron-withdrawing inductive effect of these substituents. The strength of 3-iodo-4-methylthioaniline does not vary very much from that of 3-chloro-4-methylthioaniline, indicating that the bulky iodo group is not involved in any steric interaction with the methylthio group. On the other hand, when two chloro groups (or iodo groups) are introduced in both the *ortho* positions to the methylthio group in 4-methylthioaniline, there is a large decrease in the basic strength. The decrease is much more than what is expected on the basis of the additivity of the group effects (*cf.* Table II).

The great decrease in the strength may be interpreted as follows: The methylthio group, in an attempt to be coplanar with the benzene ring, pushes away the two chloro (or iodo) groups so as to rotate freely without impediment to the resonance interaction with the *p*-amino group. The chloro (or iodo) groups thus forced away by the methylthio group, come nearer to the reaction centre and thus exert an enhanced electron-withdrawing inductive effect due to proximity. This interpretation is supported by the fact that the decrement in pK_a value due to two chloro groups is in between those due to two *meta* chloro groups (1.86) and two *ortho* chloro groups (3.50) to the amino group in 4-methylthioaniline. The same is true of 3,5-diiodo-4-methylthioaniline as well.

The presence of chloro group in the *meta* position to the amino group (in the *ortho* position to the methylsulphonyl group) in 4-methylsulphonylaniline, decreases the basic strength only due to the electron-withdrawing inductive effect of the chloro group. It can be seen (*cf.* Table II) that this decrease is almost equal to the decrease in pK_a of 3-chloro-4-methylthioaniline.

FIGURE I. CORRELATION OF $\log K/K_0$ AND HAMMETT'S σ CONSTANT FOR META SUBSTITUTED 4-METHYLTHIO- AND 4-METHYLSULPHONYLANILINES AT 30°

Furthermore, a plot of $\log K/K_0$ against σ constants for anilines containing substituents in the *meta* positions and methylthio group or methylsulphonyl group in the *para* position (σ constants of methylthio and methylsulphonyl groups are taken to be 0.06

and 1.26 respectively, as derived by Bordwell and Cooper¹²) is linear (Fig. 1). It is interesting to note that 3,5-dichloro- and 3,5-diiodo-4-methylthioanilines do not fit into the plot indicating lack of additivity of substituent effects and supporting the above mechanism.

The effect of *ortho* substituents on the strength of primary aromatic amines is not large, because of the relatively small steric requirements of the amino group and NH_3^+ group. Wepster and co-workers¹³ have shown that even such a large group as *t*-butyl group in *ortho* position to the amino group does not produce any steric inhibition to mesomerism.

2-Chloro- and 2-iodo-4-methylthioanilines are weaker than 4-methylthioaniline because of the electron-withdrawing inductive effect of the chloro and iodo groups, which exert a maximum effect from the *ortho* position. The presence of even two chloro groups in both the *ortho* positions to the reaction centre does not seem to produce any steric effect as is evident from the fact that the decrement in pK_a of 2,6-dichloro-4-methylthioaniline is approximately equal to the sum of the decreases in pK_a due to two *ortho* chloro groups (cf. Table II). It can be seen that even in the case of 2-chloro-4-methylsulphonylaniline the decrease in pK_a is almost equal to that in 2-chloro-4-methylthioaniline.

In the case of 2-nitro- and 2,6-dinitro-4-methylthioanilines, the situation is slightly different, because of the possibility for hydrogen bonding, which stabilises the free base.

Moreover, there is strong resonance interaction (direct resonance) between the powerful electron-attracting nitro-group and the *ortho* amino group, which also stabilises the free base.

12. F. G. Bordwell and G. D. Cooper, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1952, **74**, 1058.

13. J. Burgers, M. A. Hoefnagel, P. E. Verkade, H. Visser, and B. M. Wepster, *Rec. Trav. Chim.*, 1958, **77**, 491.

All these factors tend to diminish the basic strengths of 2-nitro- and 2,6-dinitro-4-methylthioanilines. In fact, in the case of 2,6-dinitro-4-methylthioaniline, the basic strength is reduced to such an extent that the pK_a has a large negative value.

FIGURE II. CORRELATION OF $\log K/K_0$ AND $\Sigma\sigma$ FOR ORTHO SUBSTITUTED 4-METHYLTHIO- AND 4-METHYLSULPHONYLANILINES AT 30°

There seems to be a linear correlation between $\log K/K_0$ values and Taft¹⁴ *ortho* substituent constants (Fig. 2). What is indeed remarkable is that even 2,5-dichloro-4-methylthioaniline does fit in very well in the plot, when $\Sigma\sigma$ is put as equal to $\sigma_{p-CH_3S} + \sigma_{m-Cl} + \sigma_{o-Cl}$. However, 2-nitro-4-methylthioaniline fits into the plot only when enhanced σ value is used, indicating "direct resonance" between the nitro and the *ortho* amino group.

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14. R. W. Taft, Jr., "Steric Effects in Organic Chemistry," M. S. Newman, ed., John Wiley and Sons, Inc., New York, 1956, p. 619.